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Asset Composition And Its Effect On Deposit Money Banks Financial Performance In Nigeria

ILOANOCHEZI, Aداugo Vivian¹ & Prof. OSUJI, Casmir Chinemerem²

¹Delta State University Business School, Asaba, Nigeria

²Banking and Finance Department,
Faculty of Management Sciences,

Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria

Corresponding Author Email: osujicasmir4@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of asset composition (AC) on the financial performance (FP) of deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria over the period 2014–2023. AC was proxied with Cash and Cash Equivalents (CCE), Loans and Advances (LAD), Interbank Deposits (IBD), Foreign Bank Deposits (FBD), and Fixed Assets (FA), while FP was measured by Return on Assets (ROA). Data were obtained from the annual reports of ten DMBs listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group with international presence. The study employed descriptive statistics, correlation, Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests, Pedroni cointegration test, and panel multiple regression (pooled, fixed, and random effects) using E-Views 9.0 at a 5% significance level. Five research questions and hypotheses were formulated and tested. Results indicated that CCE, LAD, and IBD had positive and significant effects on ROA, confirming their crucial role in enhancing bank profitability. Conversely, FBD and FA showed negative and insignificant effects on ROA, suggesting that these components do not directly contribute to improved FP. The findings highlight that maintaining liquidity through CCE and generating interest income via LAD and IBD are key drivers of profitability, while excessive reliance on foreign deposits or heavy investments in fixed assets may erode returns. The study concludes that AC significantly influences the FP of DMBs in Nigeria. It recommends that banks maintain adequate CCE levels to strengthen liquidity and enable them to take advantage of investment opportunities. Robust credit risk assessment should be adopted to improve loan quality and minimize defaults, thereby maximizing interest income. The study contributes to the literature by providing empirical evidence on the role of AC in bank profitability, emphasizing liquidity and effective loan management while cautioning against over-dependence on FBD and FA.

Keywords: Asset Composition, Cash and Cash Equivalents, Loans and Advances, Interbank Deposits, Foreign Bank Deposits, Fixed Assets and Return on Assets.

INTRODUCTION

The banking sector plays a vital role in Nigeria's economic development by serving as the main channel for mobilizing funds from savers to borrowers. The performance of banks is closely linked to their asset composition, which includes loans, investments, cash reserves, and other holdings. Assets are broadly categorized into liquid and non-liquid forms. Liquid assets such as cash, central bank reserves, and treasury bills can be converted into cash quickly and are essential for maintaining liquidity and solvency (Imo, 2021). Non-liquid assets, on the other hand, include loans, long-term investments, and fixed assets, which are often more profitable but also riskier and less liquid (Demirgüç-Kunt & Huizinga, 2018). The

composition of these assets depends on the bank's model, risk tolerance, and prevailing economic conditions, with retail banks often holding more loans while investment banks hold a larger proportion of securities (Claessens, 2018).

DMBs are key players in Nigeria's financial system, acting as intermediaries between savers and borrowers. Their performance, however, has been influenced by macroeconomic challenges such as low oil prices, inflation, and volatile exchange rates, which have negatively impacted profitability (Akinboade et al., 2021). Loans remain their major source of income, but they expose banks to credit risks, especially in an unstable economic environment. Investments in securities, corporate bonds, and equities provide diversification and additional income streams but also bring exposure to market and interest rate risks (Oludele et al., 2020). Therefore, managing the balance between risk and return in loan and investment portfolios is crucial for sustaining bank performance in Nigeria's dynamic financial landscape.

The FP of DMBs is also shaped by other components such as cash and cash equivalents, interbank deposits, foreign deposits, and fixed assets. Cash reserves provide liquidity and regulatory compliance buffers, particularly important during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic (Ogunleye & Tunde, 2021). Interbank deposits help banks adjust short-term liquidity, while foreign bank deposits improve foreign currency liquidity but are vulnerable to exchange rate fluctuations (Ojobor & Ogbonna, 2022). Fixed assets, including properties and infrastructure, contribute to long-term operational efficiency and service delivery (Ogundipe et al., 2021). A well-diversified asset portfolio enhances profitability, liquidity, and risk management, making it essential for the stability of Nigeria's banking sector. This study therefore examines the impact of these asset categories on the FP of deposit money banks in Nigeria, drawing on empirical findings to inform policymakers, regulators, and investors.

The performance of DMBs in Nigeria faces significant challenges arising from AC and accounting practices under IFRS. Issues such as exchange rate fluctuations, inconsistent accounting treatment of trading assets, and instability in financial policies weaken the reliability of financial reporting and asset valuation. Cash and cash equivalents often fail to function effectively as liquidity buffers due to economic instability, with redemption periods frequently exceeding 90 days, leading to liquidity strain. Non-performing loans remain a major setback, as loan defaults directly erode profitability and undermine financial stability. Although key financial components such as cash and cash equivalents, loans and advances, interbank deposits, foreign bank deposits, and fixed assets are central to bank performance, there is limited comprehensive research on how these factors collectively shape outcomes. While sufficient liquidity is essential for solvency (Afolabi et al., 2021), the balance between cash reserves and profitability is underexplored. Loans and advances are the main revenue sources but are vulnerable to non-performing loans (Mohammed & Ahmed, 2023). Interbank deposits can provide short-term liquidity yet expose banks to risks (Ugochukwu & Okwu, 2022), while foreign bank deposits affect profitability and risk diversification but lack empirical clarity. Fixed assets such as infrastructure and technology may improve efficiency but can also reduce margins if poorly managed (Jain et al., 2022). Thus, there is a pressing need for systematic investigation into how these asset categories influence FP, particularly ROA, within Nigeria's volatile economic environment.

Conceptual Review

Bank Assets Composition

The bank AC comprises of the liquid and non-liquid assets which are the focused of this study. Bank liquid AC is a critical aspect of a bank's financial health and stability (Gamayuni, 2018). The composition of a bank's liquid assets can have a significant impact on its ability to meet its short-term obligations and withstand financial shocks. In this review of literature, we will explore 5 key components of bank liquid and non-liquid AC and examine recent research and findings on this topic.

Cash and Cash Equivalents: Cash and cash equivalents are the most liquid assets of banks, comprising physical cash, demand deposits, and highly liquid securities such as Treasury bills and commercial paper. They are vital for meeting daily operations, maintaining depositor confidence, and ensuring quick access to funds during financial stress (Mihail, 2019). Regulatory frameworks like Basel III require banks to hold minimum liquidity through the Liquidity Coverage Ratio (BIS, 2011), prompting institutions to

strengthen liquidity management. Their composition reflects operational needs, risk appetite, and market conditions (Jones, 2022). In stable times, banks may invest in slightly higher-yielding equivalents, while in crises they increase reserves (Smith & Thompson, 2023). Thus, cash and equivalents underpin stability, solvency, and regulatory compliance.

Loans and Advances: Loans and advances are credit facilities banks provide to individuals and businesses, including commercial and consumer loans. Though less liquid than other assets, they are vital for generating income and driving economic growth (Onyeka, Nnado & Iroegbu, 2018). Loans are typically long-term, while advances are short-term credit facilities. These instruments support financial intermediation by channeling funds from savers to borrowers, stimulating investment and consumption. The sector has evolved with digital platforms, peer-to-peer lending, and big data credit scoring, enhancing access and risk management (Kumar & Bansal, 2022). However, non-performing loans, especially during downturns, pose risks to stability (World Bank, 2023). Thus, loans and advances remain central to banking profitability and economic development.

Interbank Deposits: Interbank deposits are short-term funds that banks place with other financial institutions to manage liquidity and meet reserve requirements. They serve as a vital buffer, providing funding while mitigating risks from fluctuations in deposits and withdrawals (Sathyamoorthi & Dzimir, 2020). Conducted through the interbank market, these transactions help banks optimize balance sheets and maintain solvency (Berger et al., 2021). Central bank policies, such as interest rates and reserve requirements, directly influence interbank lending rates like LIBOR or SOFR (Dahlgren & Ehlers, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic underscored their importance, with central banks intervening to stabilize markets (Brunnermeier & Sannikov, 2020). Overall, interbank deposits are essential for liquidity management, risk mitigation, and sustaining financial and macroeconomic stability.

Foreign Bank Deposit: Foreign bank deposits are funds placed by banks, individuals, corporations, or governments in banks outside their home country, often to diversify funding, manage liquidity, and earn additional interest income (Afza & Nazir, 2019). They facilitate international trade, investment, and serve as a hedge against currency and economic volatility (Hale & Obstfeld, 2016). Their dynamics are shaped by macroeconomic conditions, monetary policies, political stability, and regulatory frameworks (Cetorelli & Goldberg, 2012). In emerging markets, foreign deposits support financing and financial inclusion, though regulations like FATCA and CRS have tightened compliance requirements, affecting attractiveness (Zucman, 2014). Overall, foreign deposits remain vital for international banking, offering benefits while posing challenges linked to transparency and global financial stability.

Fixed Assets: Fixed assets, also known as non-current assets, are critical to banks' operations as they include properties, equipment, and infrastructure used in daily activities. These assets support income generation, service delivery, and long-term stability, unlike current assets that are easily liquidated (Vozkova & Teply, 2018). Proper management and valuation of fixed assets influence financial statements, return on equity, and regulatory compliance. Guided by IFRS and GAAP (IASB, 2020), banks must recognize, measure, and report these assets accurately. Recent trends, including digital transformation and the COVID-19 pandemic, have prompted greater investment in technology-related fixed assets such as digital platforms and cybersecurity (KPMG, 2021). Effective asset management enhances efficiency, competitiveness, and FP.

Financial Performance (FP)

FP can be measured using several indicators, including ROE, ROA, ROI, net profit margin, and earnings per share. For the purpose of this study, emphasis is placed on ROE and ROA. ROE is a key profitability metric that measures how effectively a firm uses shareholders' equity to generate profits. It is calculated as net income divided by equity, reflecting management's efficiency in utilizing owners' funds (Nisar et al 2018). A low ROE suggests poor utilization of equity and failure to meet shareholder wealth maximization, while a high ROE indicates effective management and profitability (Rahman, Uddin & Moudud-UI-Huq, 2018). ROE is particularly useful in comparing performance across firms in the same industry, as it reveals the intensity of management's ability to generate income from equity (Damankah & Eliasu, 2018).

ROA, on the other hand, measures how efficiently a bank utilizes its assets to generate net income. It is calculated as net income divided by total assets and is typically expressed as a percentage (Bagh et al., 2017; Bapat & Sagar, 2018). ROA reflects the operational effectiveness and financial health of an institution by showing how well it converts its asset base, comprising loans, securities, and cash—into earnings (González, 2021). In banking, ROA is crucial because assets largely represent revenue-generating activities. High ROA values indicate stronger profitability relative to asset size, signaling efficiency and sound management (Bourke, 2022). Factors such as interest rate changes, regulatory shifts, and digital transformation influence ROA, with diversified asset portfolios often producing more stable results (Chen & Chen, 2023). Understanding ROA provides insights into past performance while helping stakeholders forecast profitability and stability in a dynamic financial environment.

Theoretical Review

Financial Hierarchy Theory (FHT)

The FHT, introduced by Donaldson (1961) and expanded by Myers and Majluf (1984), also known as the Pecking Order Theory, emphasizes firms' preference for financing: internal funds first, followed by debt, and equity as the last option. It links liquidity management to capital structure and highlights the importance of cash holdings in imperfect markets (Adegbe, 2021). For deposit money banks in Nigeria, this theory explains how asset composition, including cash and cash equivalents, loans and advances, interbank deposits, foreign bank deposits, and fixed assets, affects FP measured by ROA. Adequate liquidity improves stability but may reduce returns, while loans increase profitability but carry credit risks. Interbank and foreign deposits enhance liquidity yet pose interest rate and currency risks. Fixed assets support efficiency but can reduce ROA. Effective asset management under this framework improves performance.

Modern Portfolio Theory

The MPT, introduced by Markowitz in 1952, emphasizes diversification to minimize unsystematic risk while maximizing returns for a given level of risk. It assumes investors aim to optimize returns by holding uncorrelated assets, though its rational investor assumption is a limitation (Bereh et al., 2020). For deposit money banks in Nigeria, MPT is relevant in analyzing asset composition, including cash, loans, interbank deposits, foreign deposits, and fixed assets, with performance measured by ROA. Diversifying loan portfolios reduces default risks, while balancing cash holdings ensures liquidity without sacrificing profitability. Interbank and foreign deposits provide yields but expose banks to liquidity and currency risks. Fixed assets enhance operational efficiency but must be efficiently managed. Applying MPT helps banks optimize risk, returns, and long-term financial stability.

Empirical Review

Nwankwo and Eze (2023) examined the effect of AC on the financial stability of Nigerian banks using loans and investments as proxies, with stability measured by Z-score. Employing a longitudinal design and regression analysis on data from 2010 to 2022 sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria, they found that a higher proportion of loans in banks' AC significantly improved financial stability. They recommended expanding loan portfolios as a means of strengthening bank stability.

Ogunbiyi and Akinyemi (2023) studied the effect of asset structure on Nigerian banks' performance, using current and non-current assets as proxies, while measuring performance with Net Profit Margin. Employing a descriptive design with regression and correlation on 2014–2022 annual report data, findings revealed that current assets strongly and positively influenced profitability, while non-current assets had weaker effects. They recommended maintaining a higher ratio of current assets, as this enhances profitability and sustains financial efficiency.

Akanbi and Afolabi (2023) investigated the relationship between asset allocation and FP in Nigerian banks. Asset allocation was measured using equity and debt securities, with ROA as the performance indicator. Using exploratory research and OLS regression on 2015–2022 bank reports, the study found equity investments significantly boosted performance compared to debt securities. They recommended

banks prioritize equity investments for stronger returns, emphasizing that strategic asset allocation directly impacts financial outcomes in Nigerian banks.

Adebayo and Ogunleye (2023) analyzed the impact of AC on Nigerian banks' performance, proxied by cash, loans, and investments, with ROE as the measure. Using longitudinal design and time series analysis of 2010–2022 financial statements, they found a significant positive relationship between loan portfolios and ROE. The study concluded that expanding loan portfolios would directly enhance FP and recommended banks strategically increase lending to optimize profitability while managing associated risks effectively.

Okafor and Igbokwe (2023) explored how asset structure affects Nigerian banks' FP, using Net Interest Margin and Total Income as indicators. Applying a longitudinal design and analyzing 2010–2020 banking sector annual reports with descriptive and inferential statistics, they found diversified asset structures improved performance, especially investments in government securities. The study concluded banks with diversified asset portfolios achieve better outcomes compared to concentrated ones, recommending greater diversification as a strategy to mitigate risks and boost returns.

Daniel and Raji (2023) studied the relationship between asset categories and operational efficiency of Nigerian banks. Cash reserves, loans, and investments were examined against the cost-to-income ratio using cross-sectional design and structural equation modeling. Data from 2018–2022 NDIC and bank reports revealed loans significantly improved efficiency, while excessive cash reserves increased costs. They recommended banks optimize asset allocation by strategically expanding lending while maintaining moderate cash reserves to achieve stronger operational outcomes and financial efficiency.

Akanbi (2023) investigated asset composition's effect on Nigerian commercial banks' profitability, using current and non-current assets as predictors of ROA and ROE. Adopting a quantitative cross-sectional design with OLS regression, the study analyzed data from 2000 to 2022 across 15 banks and CBN databases. Findings revealed non-current assets had a greater influence on profitability compared to current assets. The study emphasized aligning AC toward long-term investments to maximize profitability and strengthen overall bank performance.

Nworie et al. (2023) examined the impact of asset management on FP of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Using a causal-comparative design, they analyzed debtor turnover, cash ratio, and inventory turnover against EPS from 2011 to 2020 for 12 sampled firms. Results showed debtor and inventory turnover positively affected EPS, while cash ratio had a negative effect. Although effects were statistically insignificant, the study advised firms to improve debt collection efficiency to increase profitability.

Nworie and Ofoje (2022) assessed the impact of inventory conversion period, accounts receivable period, and current ratio on ROA of Nigerian food and beverage companies. Using a random effect model and data from six enterprises, findings revealed inventory conversion time had a significant negative impact on ROA. Conversely, current ratio and receivable period showed positive but insignificant effects. The study suggested reducing inventory conversion time as a strategy to improve profitability and financial efficiency.

Ojo and Adeyemi (2022) investigated the impact of asset structure on the FP of Nigerian banks. Asset structure proxied with short-term vs. long-term assets while FP proxied ROE. Cross-sectional research design was adopted in this study and the data was c from 10 banks for the period 2016-2021, analyzed with Panel data analysis. The results showed that Short-term assets positively impacted ROE, while long-term assets had a mixed effect. Thereby recommends that banks should balance their asset structure to optimize performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the ex-post facto research design, which examines the impact of past factors on current events. It relies on secondary data analysis, since the occurrences have already taken place. Annual reports and accounts of ten Nigerian banks were analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques. This design is suitable because it allows for the investigation of cause-and-effect relationships without manipulating variables, focusing instead on historical data to understand the influence of AC on banks' FP in Nigeria. The study population consists of 19 banks listed on the NGX as of May 31, 2023, according to

the CBN press release. These banks represent the entire deposit money banking sector in Nigeria and form the finite population for the study. The choice of this population ensures that the findings are relevant and applicable to the overall Nigerian banking system, thereby providing comprehensive insights into how AC affects FP across the sector.

From the population of 19 banks, a sample of 10 banks was selected, representing 52.63% of the total. The researcher adopted the convenience sampling technique, a form of non-probability sampling. This was chosen due to ease of access to annual reports and the challenges of computing financial ratios across all banks. Despite its limitations, the researcher considered the sample size adequate to make valid conclusions, as it captures more than half of the population and provides sufficient data for meaningful analysis. The study relied on secondary data, sourced from the annual reports of banks listed on the NGX. Quantitative financial data spanning 2014 to 2023 were collected to capture trends over time. These reports provided details on AC and FP, forming the basis for statistical analysis. Secondary data was chosen because it is reliable, readily available, and consistent with previous empirical studies in the field, making it appropriate for investigating long-term relationships among the selected variables.

Quantitative methods were employed, combining descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analysis to examine relationships between variables. The study tested for stationarity using unit root tests and applied diagnostic checks before conducting panel least squares regression with OLS in E-Views 9.0. Both pooled multiple regression and co-integration tests were used to assess long-run relationships. Panel least squares regression explained variations in ROA as the dependent variable, based on changes in asset composition, while assuming a linear relationship between the variables. The regression model was adapted from Duru, Okpe, and Andrew (2022), who studied asset management and FP. While their model used three independent variables, this study expanded it to five: Cash and Cash Equivalents (CCE), Loans and Advances (LAD), Interbank Deposits (IBD), Foreign Bank Deposits (FBD), and Fixed Assets (FA). The dependent variable is Return on Assets (ROA). The model is specified as:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogCCE} + \beta_2 \text{LogLAD} + \beta_3 \text{LogIBD} + \beta_4 \text{LogFBD} + \beta_5 \text{LogFA} + E$$

Where β_0 is the intercept, β_1 – β_5 coefficients, and E the error term.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics summarize key dataset features through measures of central tendency (mean, median, mode) and variability (range, variance, standard deviation). In time series analysis, they help reveal trends, seasonal patterns, and anomalies, providing a foundation for deeper statistical and econometric investigations.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	ROA	LOGCCE	LOGLAD	LOGIBD	LOGFBD	LOGFA
Mean	3.302699	6.965898	7.478182	7.654328	6.995936	7.594614
Median	0.017159	6.810235	8.095551	8.369305	7.685759	7.715992
Maximum	27.69292	9.532312	9.151437	9.281209	8.766669	10.48046
Minimum	-0.074699	2.961895	4.995683	4.995258	4.854324	5.209239
Std. Dev.	2.766995	1.904263	1.358780	1.367481	1.396817	1.325714
Skewness	9.846043	-0.349346	-0.378242	-0.395954	-0.307120	0.057214
Kurtosis	9.796671	1.884560	1.429572	1.443838	1.329686	1.480065
Jarque-Bera	39193.56	7.218244	12.66046	12.70316	12.80093	9.680406
Probability	0.000000	0.027076	0.001782	0.001744	0.001661	0.007905
Sum	30.26990	696.5898	747.8182	765.4328	678.6058	759.4614
Sum Sq. Dev.	757.9700	358.9954	182.7819	185.1305	187.3053	173.9944
Observations	100	100	100	100	97	100

Source: EVIEW, 9.0 Outputs, 2025.

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics. ROA shows a mean of 3.3027 with a Std. Dev. of 2.7670. CCE has a mean of 6.9659 and standard deviation of 1.9043, LAD 7.4782 and 1.3588, IBD 7.6543 and 1.3675, FBD 6.9959 and 1.3968, while FA records 7.5946 and 1.3257. Since all standard deviations are lower than their means, the data are not widely dispersed. Regarding kurtosis, ROA exhibits thick tails as its coefficient exceeds 3, whereas CCE, LAD, IBD, FBD, and FA display thin tails with values below 3, indicating closer alignment with normal distribution.

Correlation Matrix

Correlation measures the strength and direction of linear relationships between variables, aiding in identifying potential links for causality and predictive analysis. A correlation matrix shows the degree (weak, moderate, strong) and direction (positive, negative, zero) of these relationships. Table 2 presents the study’s correlation matrix.

Table 2: Correlation Output

	ROA	LOGCCE	LOGLAD	LOGIBD	LOGFBD	LOGFA
ROA	1.000000					
LOGCCE	0.123886	1.000000				
LOGLAD	0.082786	0.733466	1.000000			
LOGIBD	0.147334	0.771438	0.763372	1.000000		
LOGFBD	-0.110147	0.752076	0.761142	0.784472	1.000000	
LOGFA	-0.120879	0.286318	0.374730	0.414012	0.405590	1.000000

Source: EVIEW, 9.0 Outputs, 2025.

The correlation matrix in Table 2 shows that CCE, LAD, and IBD are positively correlated with ROA of Nigerian DMBs, while FBD and FA exhibit negative correlations. IBD recorded the highest coefficient of 0.1473, indicating a relatively stronger positive relationship with ROA compared to other variables. Since all correlation values are below 0.7, multicollinearity is absent. Overall, the results suggest that while CCE, LAD, and IBD positively influence ROA, FBD and FA negatively affect banks’ FP.

Panel Unit Root Test

This test examines whether the data series are stationary, as non-stationary data can yield unreliable and invalid results. To ensure accuracy, a panel unit root test was conducted using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) method. The summarized outcomes of this stationarity test are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: ADF Panel Unit Root Test

Variables	Method	ADF Statistics	Probability	@ Level	Check for Stationary
ROA	ADF Test	59.2525	0.7181	1(0)	Non-Stationary
CCE	ADF Test	15.6061	0.7407	1(0)	Non-Stationary
LAD	ADF Test	15.0188	0.7753	1(0)	Non-Stationary
IBD	ADF Test	35.5245	0.0775	1(0)	Non-Stationary
FBD	ADF Test	33.2401	0.0717	1(0)	Non-Stationary
FA	ADF Test	24.1053	0.2378	1(0)	Non-Stationary
Variables	Method	Statistics	Probability	@1st Diff.	Check for Stationary
ROA	ADF Test	67.7688	0.0000	1(1)	Stationary
CCE	ADF Test	32.1797	0.0414	1(1)	Stationary
LAD	ADF Test	28.8260	0.0012	1(1)	Stationary
IBD	ADF Test	24.5161	0.0206	1(1)	Stationary
FBD	ADF Test	39.1511	0.0027	1(1)	Stationary
FA	ADF Test	37.0240	0.0116	1(1)	Stationary

Source: E-Views 9.0 Output, (2025).

Table 3 presents the panel unit root test for the independent variables (CCE, LAD, IBD, FBD, and FA) and the dependent variable (ROA) of the ten DMBs listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The null hypothesis assumes non-stationarity. Results from the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test indicate probability values lower than the 5% significance level, leading to rejection of the null hypothesis. Although the series were not stationary at level, they became stationary at first difference. Thus, the data

series are confirmed to be stationary, normally distributed, and appropriate for further analysis using multiple panel regression techniques.

Pedroni Panel Cointegration Test Results

The first-difference values from the panel unit root test show that all variables became stationary, leading to rejection of the null hypothesis at the 5% significance level. Thus, the variables are integrated of order one [I(1)], justifying the application of the Pedroni panel cointegration test presented below.

Table 4: Pedroni Panel Cointegration Test Results

Series: ROA LOGCCE LOGLAD LOGIBD LOGFBD LOGFA
 Date: 12/06/25 Time: 10:05
 Sample: 2014 2023
 Included observations: 100

Cross-sections included: 9 (1 dropped)
 Null Hypothesis: No cointegration
 Trend assumption: No deterministic trend
 User-specified lag length: 1
 Newey-West automatic bandwidth selection and Bartlett kernel

Alternative hypothesis: common AR coeffs. (within-dimension)

	<u>Statistic</u>	<u>Prob.</u>	Weighted	<u>Statistic</u>	<u>Prob.</u>
Panel v-Statistic	-1.208221	0.8865		-1.484216	0.9311
Panel rho-Statistic	4.359870	1.0000		3.220142	0.9994
Panel PP-Statistic	0.007257	0.5029		-7.218392	0.0000
Panel ADF-Statistic	0.386762	0.6505		-3.633151	0.0001

Alternative hypothesis: individual AR coeffs. (between-dimension)

	<u>Statistic</u>	<u>Prob.</u>
Group rho-Statistic	4.489443	1.0000
Group PP-Statistic	-16.45615	0.0000
Group ADF-Statistic	-5.035402	0.0000

Source: E-VIEW, 9.0 Outputs, 2025.

The Pedroni panel cointegration test results in Table 4.5 show that the coefficients of panel ADF and group PP statistics were significant at the 5% level. Consequently, the null hypothesis of no cointegration among the variables is rejected for both panel and group statistics. This confirms the presence of a long-run relationship among the study variables. Additionally, the results address the unit root problem, as the ADF probability values are below 0.05, indicating stationarity. Hence, the data are suitable for further analysis through multiple panel regression, supporting the validity and reliability of the study's econometric model.

Regression Result Analysis

Using regression coefficients and p-values. Three regression models; pooled, fixed, and random effects were employed. To determine the most appropriate model, the Redundant Fixed Effects Test and the Correlated Random Effects Hausman Test were conducted, with results presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Redundant Fixed Effects Tests and Correlated Hausman Test

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests				
Equation: Untitled				
Test cross-section fixed effects				
Effects Test		Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F		1.901325	(9,82)	0.0531
Cross-section Chi-square		18.384458	9	0.0310
Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test				
Equation: Untitled				
Test cross-section random effects				
Test Summary		Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random		2.388190	5	0.7932

Source: Extracted from E-VIEW Outputs, 2025.

In Table 5, the study employs panel data analysis to determine whether a random-effects or fixed-effects model provides a more suitable estimation framework. The results indicate that the fixed-effects model is the most appropriate for this analysis. This conclusion is supported by the fixed-effects test, which produced a Chi-square statistic of 18.3845, exceeding the threshold value of 10 and a corresponding p-value of 0.0310, which is below the conventional 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the fixed-effects model is considered the optimal specification for analyzing the panel data derived from the ten (10) selected Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) included in this study.

Table 6: Fixed Effect Pooled Regression

Dependent Variable: ROA
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 12/06/25 Time: 10:00
 Sample: 2014 2023
 Periods included: 10
 Cross-sections included: 10
 Total panel (unbalanced) observations: 97

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	5.836433	2.275376	2.565041	0.0031
LOGCCE	0.148182	0.032184	4.604213	0.0001
LOGLAD	6.848368	0.464781	14.73462	0.0000
LOGIBD	5.736845	0.859328	6.675964	0.0000
LOGFBD	-0.074782	0.766800	-0.097525	0.9225
LOGFA	-0.044296	0.444654	-0.099619	0.9209
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.774615	Mean dependent var		0.312143
Adjusted R-squared	0.736135	S.D. dependent var		2.809339
S.E. of regression	1.443097	Akaike info criterion		3.712747
Sum squared resid	170.7674	Schwarz criterion		4.110898
Log likelihood	-165.0682	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.873739
F-statistic	20.13012	Durbin-Watson stat		1.883823
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Extracted from E-VIEW Outputs, 2025.

The Table 6 shows the regression between the dependent variable which is FP proxied with ROA and independent variables identified as measures of AC proxied with CCE, LAD, IBD, FBD and FA.

The findings show that CCE have a significant positive effect on ROA ($\beta=0.1482$; $p<0.0001$). Adequate cash reserves provide liquidity, meet regulatory requirements, and act as a buffer against shocks, enhancing stability and profitability. While returns are lower than loans, CCE support operational flexibility and immediate investments. Financial hierarchy theory highlights their role in prioritizing low-risk financing, while modern portfolio theory views them as stabilizers in asset diversification. This aligns with Okafor and Igbokwe (2023).

LAD significantly and positively influence ROA ($\beta=6.8484$; $p<0.0000$). As the main revenue source, loans generate interest income that drives profitability, provided credit risks are effectively managed. Expanding loan portfolios strengthens performance, consistent with financial hierarchy theory's preference for efficient internal financing. Modern portfolio theory recognizes loans as high-risk, high-return assets that, when diversified, optimize the risk-return tradeoff. This finding is supported by Nwankwo and Eze (2023), Adebayo and Ogunleye (2023), and Daniel and Raji (2023).

IBD also show a significant positive relationship with ROA ($\beta=5.7368$; $p<0.0000$). They enable banks to manage liquidity effectively, profit from interest rate differentials, and meet short-term obligations while earning returns. Financial hierarchy theory views IBD as strategic liquidity tools, while modern portfolio theory sees them as risk-balancing instruments in asset-liability management. These findings are consistent with Okafor and Igbokwe (2023).

FBD, however, display an insignificant negative effect on ROA ($\beta=-0.0748$; $p>0.9225$). Increased foreign deposits fail to improve asset efficiency due to transaction costs, regulatory burdens, and currency risks. Financial hierarchy theory suggests these factors undermine efficiency, while modern portfolio theory highlights the risks of exchange rate volatility and geopolitical instability. Misalignment with strategic objectives explains their adverse effect. This supports Ojo and Adeyemi (2022).

FA also show an insignificant negative relationship with ROA ($\beta=-0.04430$; $p>0.9209$). Though essential for operations, fixed assets reduce profitability due to depreciation, maintenance costs, and limited flexibility in adapting to market changes. Financial hierarchy theory links this to costly resource allocation, while modern portfolio theory stresses opportunity costs of capital tied in non-liquid assets. Misallocation weakens ROA, consistent with Ojo and Adeyemi (2022).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the effect of AC on the FP of DMBs in Nigeria between 2014 and 2023. AC was proxied with CCE, LAD, IBD, FBD, and FA, while FP was measured by ROA. Results revealed that CCE, LAD, and IBD have positive and significant effects on ROA, while FBD and FA showed negative and insignificant effects on ROA. The following recommendations are made:

1. Banks should prioritize maintaining adequate levels of CCE to ensure they can capitalize on investment opportunities and manage risks effectively.
2. Banks should implement robust credit risk assessment frameworks to enhance the quality of their loan portfolios, thereby maximizing interest income and improving ROA.
3. Banks should actively engage in interbank lending and borrowing to optimize their asset utilization and enhance profitability.
4. Banks should critically evaluate their reliance on foreign bank deposits and consider strategies to mitigate associated risks and costs.
5. Banks should adopt a more strategic approach to investing in fixed assets, ensuring that such investments align with their overall profitability goals.

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